

Carbon Nanotubes with Dual Wall Structure; Properties and Fracture Behavior of Epoxy Nanocomposites

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SUMMARY

Epoxy-based nanocomposites were prepared using two different MWCNT with different manufacturing routes and structures. Both CNTs were subjected to a UV/ozone treatment and the changes in surface functionality and morphology were characterized. Various functional and mechanical properties as well as fracture resistance were measured and compared between the nanocomposites containing different CNTs. Their merits and weaknesses were identified. The implications of these findings and toughening mechanisms are discussed.

Keywords: nanocomposites, carbon nanotubes, UV/Ozone treatment, fracture toughness, mechanical properties

1. INTRODUCTION

Owing to their exceptional mechanical and physical properties, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are considered as an ideal nano-reinforcement for polymers [1-2]. Significant research has been directed towards understanding the mechanical and functional behaviours of CNT nanocomposites in the past decade. It has been well established that dispersion of CNTs in polymer plays a very important role in controlling the mechanical, thermal and electrical characteristics of the nanocomposites. CNTs tend to agglomerate without proper wetting when mixed together with polymers unless they are properly functionalized because of the strong van der Waals forces among them and inherently inert nature of CNTs. Upon loading, these CNT agglomerates encourage premature failure of the composite at a much lower stress than expected. Chemical or physical modifications of CNT surface, such as amino functionalization or surfactant treatment, are found to be effective in improving the dispersion of CNTs in epoxy, resulting in improvement of the mechanical properties [3-4]. An investigation on MWCNT/polyimide nanocomposites indicated that both pristine and plasma treated CNTs gave improvement in tensile properties. It was shown that the dispersion of CNTs in polyimide was improved after plasma treatment and so were the tensile properties of the composite [5]. However, CNT contents above 0.5wt% resulted in severe agglomeration with an associated reduction in mechanical properties of the composite. CNT dispersion also affected the electrical and thermal properties of the nanocomposites. Improvement in CNT dispersion on both the macroscopic and nanoscopic scales gave rise to

a lowered percolation threshold from 1.0% to 0.1wt% due to the formation of CNT networks throughout the insulating matrix material [6].

This paper is a part of our on going research work on CNT based nanocomposites. The main focus here is to evaluate the effect of the CNT morphologies on their dispersion states in the polymers and properties of the nanocomposites. Epoxy-based nanocomposites were prepared using two different MWCNT with different manufacturing routes and structures. Both CNTs were subjected to a UV/ozone treatment and the changes in surface functionality and morphology were characterized. Various functional and mechanical properties as well as fracture resistance were measured and compared between the nanocomposites containing different CNTs. Their merits and weaknesses were identified.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Materials and fabrication of nanocomposites

Two types of multi-walled CNTs with different manufacturing routes and structures were used as the reinforcements for the nanocomposite. One of them was vapor grown, and had outer diameters and length ranging between 40-60nm and 20 μm , respectively. It had a straight, less-entangled bamboo-like structure (designated hereafter as “CNT A”). The other CNT was basically the same as that employed previously [3,7], which was prepared through a chemical vapor deposition method, and had diameters and lengths ranging between 10–20 nm and 10–50 μm , respectively. This CNT was highly entangled and had a vermicular structure (designated hereafter as “CNT B”). The purity of both types was about 95%, according to the manufacturer’s specifications, and the aspect ratio was only marginally higher for CNT B than CNT A judging from the known dimensions. SEM and TEM micrographs of these CNTs are presented in Figures 1 and 2, showing the differences in their morphologies and nanoscopic structures.

The purification and basic treatment of the two nanotubes were same as reported previously [7] As received CNTs were purified by ultrasonication in a sonication bath (Branson 150) using acetone as a solvent. After drying, both CNTs were subjected to a UV/Ozone treatment for different duration and the changes in surface functionality and morphology were characterized.

Depending upon the degree of entanglement of these CNTs, different processing routes were adopted after UV/Ozone treatment as the optimized conditions after many preliminary studies. CNT A were much less entangled and could easily be dispersed, and therefore after UV/Ozone treatment no further treatment was carried out. The reduction and silane-functionalization processes used for the highly entangled CNT B were developed in our previous study [8].

For the preparation of the nanocomposite coating, either type of CNTs were added into a preheated epoxy resin with varying CNT contents and the mixture was sonicated for 1 hr, followed by degassing in a vacuum oven at 70°C. The stoichiometric amount of the curing agent, 14.5 part per hundred of epoxy, was added into the CNT-epoxy mixture to prepare the nanocomposites. The mixture was casted into the flat mould that consisted of two parallel aluminum plates and a Teflon dam of a thickness of ~3 mm. The mould was cured at 80 °C for 2 hr and post-cured at 150 °C for 3 hr.

2.2 Characterization of nanocomposites

The surface chemistry of the untreated and treated CNTs was evaluated by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, surface analysis PHI 5600) and Raman spectroscopy (Renishaw, RM 3000). In the XPS analysis, a monochromatic Al K α X-ray was used at 14 kV. The 514 nm Argon ion laser excitation source (focused to a spot size of 2 μ m) was used to scan the samples from 500 cm⁻¹ to 4000 cm⁻¹ at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ and thus the Raman spectra were obtained.

The flexural strength of the epoxy and nanocomposites were determined according to the procedure specified in ASTM standard D790. The moulded epoxy or nanocomposite plates were cut into 80 mm long x 12.7 mm wide x 3 mm thick specimens that were subjected to bending with a support span of 50 mm and at a cross-head speed of 1.3 mm/min on a universal testing machine (MTS Sintech 10/D). Charpy impact resistance tests were performed on the notched specimens prepared according to the specifications, ASTM D6110 standard test method. The specimens for the impact test were cut into dimensions of 127 mm long \times 12.7 mm wide \times 3 mm thick, with a \sim 2.7 mm deep notch at the mid-edge of the specimen. The impact tests were performed on a machine (Zwick-Roell HIT515P) with an impactor of 2.7 J energy. The electrical conductivity of neat epoxy and nanocomposites was measured at room temperature based on four probe method using square samples (10 mm X 10mm, 1mm thick). The glass transition temperatures, T_g , of nanocomposites were obtained from the maxima of the tan δ curves, determined using a dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA-7, Perkin Elmer), according to the specification, ASTM Standard D4065. The neat epoxy and nanocomposite samples with dimensions 20mm long \times 3mm wide \times 1mm thick were tested in three point bending at varying temperatures between ambient and 200 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min and a frequency of 1.0 Hz in a nitrogen atmosphere. Minimum five specimens were tested for each set of conditions.

A transmission electron microscope (TEM, JEOL 2010) was used to observe the morphology of carbon nanotubes. The dispersion of carbon and morphology of fracture surfaces of the impact test samples were examined by using Jeol 6700 and JEOL 6300F field emission scanning electron microscopes, respectively. Surface roughness of impact fracture surfaces were measured using an optical Profiler, Wyko NT3300 from Veeco Instruments Inc, having vertical measurement range of 0.1 μ m to 1mm. At least 10 scan were performed for each material at different positions and the average roughness was calculated using Wyko vision software.

3. RESULTS and DISCUSSION

3.1 Morphology of carbon nanotubes

Fig.1 shows the morphologies of as-received CNTs. In order to identify their difference, the same level of magnification was used. The image of CNT A (Fig. 1a) indicates that they were much less aggregated and the structures of individual carbon nanotubes can be clearly seen. On the other hand, It was noticed that CNT B were closely packed, highly entangled bundles of thin CNTs as it was difficult to visualize the structures in the as-received

condition (Fig.1b). The TEM images given in Fig. 2 indicate marked differences in terms of shape, size and diameter. CNT A were thick-walled, straight and have bamboo like shapes (Fig. 2a), whereas CNT B (Fig.2b) were thin and vermicular in shape.

Fig.1 SEM micrographs of two types of carbon nanotubes; (a) CNT A and (b) CNT B

Fig.3, show the images of the tube wall of CNT A and CNT B at higher magnifications. For CNT A, two regions of different morphologies are clearly observed (Fig3c). The inner walls of the tubes consisted of regular graphene layers, similar to those observed for most of the multi-walled carbon nanotubes; the d spacing between these layers was about 3.35 \AA . The outer region of the tube wall was composed of irregular graphene layers with a d spacing of more than 3.35 \AA , resembling the turbostratic carbon structure of some of the carbon materials.

Fig. 2. TEM micrographs showing morphologies of CNTs; (a) CNT A and (b) CNT B

3.2 Surface Chemistry

The surface chemistry of carbon nanotubes was evaluated by XPS. The XPS general spectra of as received CNT A and CNT B are represented in Fig 4a, showing that both CNTs share significant similarities. Along with C1s, the peak for graphitic carbon was at 284.5eV, oxygen (peak at the binding energy of 533eV) was identified which would have resulted from functional groups containing -C-O- linkage. CNT A, however, has a stronger peak indicating that it has a higher concentration of oxygen functionalities. The atomic concentrations (%) of as received CNT A are presented in table 1 indicating that the basic surface chemistry of CNT A was similar to CNT B and other pristine carbon nanotubes [7]. The O/C ratios for the different exposure times are plotted as a function of UV/Ozone exposure time in Fig. 4b. Both carbon nanotubes exhibited a large increase in oxygen surface functionalities for the first 30 minutes, the increase in O/C ratio was similar. After this, there was a marked difference in the behaviour of the two carbon nanotubes; CNT B exhibited a small change after 30minutes and reached saturation after 1 hour. For CNT A the O/C ratio increased even up to 2 hours, indicating a higher reactivity of CNT A due to the turbostatic carbon layers.

Fig. 3. TEM micrographs showing wall structures of CNTs; (a, c) CNT A and (b), CNT B

Raman spectroscopy was employed to measure the change in the state of disorder before and after UV/Ozone treatment. It is well known that the Raman spectra of the CNTs exhibit two characteristics bands, the G band (1580 cm^{-1}) and D band at (1350 cm^{-1}). The D band is a (of the?) double-resonance Raman mode, which can be considered as a measurement of structural disorder coming from amorphous carbon and other defects [9]. The G band originates from the tangential in-plane stretching vibrations of the carbon-carbon bonds within the graphene sheets. The ratio of intensities of the D and G bands, R/D , is used to evaluate the disorder density of the nanotube walls. Table 3 gives the intensities for the D and G bands of the CNT A before and after UV/Ozone treatment; these are compared with CNT B exposed to UV/Ozone light for similar durations. Owing to the variance of turbostatic layer thickness in homogeneity, some differences in the D/G ratios was observed for CNT A, therefore average values are presented in the table. For untreated CNT A, it ranged from 8.3 to 9.0, always higher than untreated CNT B showing larger defects and covalently bonded surface functionalities [10]. The D/G ratios for the treated carbon nanotubes further confirmed that there was an increase in defect sites for CNT A up to 2 hours whereas no change was observed for CNT B.

Fig 4: (a) XPS general spectra of untreated CNTs; and (b) O/C ratios vs. UV/Ozone exposure time, data for CNT B after [7].

Table1. Atomic concentrations (%) of elements of CNT A before and after UV/Ozone treatment

Treatment	C1s	O1s	N1s	O/C ratio
CNT A (as recd.)	96.34	3.11	0	0.032
UV/Ozone_30min	91.36	8.01	0.12	0.088
UV/Ozone_01hr	88.94	10.37	0.12	0.118
UV/Ozone_2hrs	87.58	11.66	0.2	0.133

3.3 Mechanical Properties of Nanocomposites.

The flexural properties are plotted as a function of CNT content as shown in Fig. 5. The flexural strength increases with increasing CNT content, reaching a maximum at 0.5wt%. Also superimposed on Fig. 5(a) are the flexural strengths measured previously for thin walled CNT B [8]. It is worth noting that even the heavily functionalised CNTs with a silane coupling agent were not able to extend the strength improvement of the nanocomposite beyond the CNT content of 0.3wt%. This indicates that the inherent morphological structure of CNTs is a single dominant parameter that controls the dispersion in a polymer matrix although the improved surface functionality may also promote dispersion to a certain extent

Some improvements in the flexural modulus were observed with increasing CNT A content. The trend exhibited by untreated or silane treated CNT B were similar to the changes observed for CNT A; where silane treated carbon nanotubes exhibited the best results because the inherent modulus of nanoparticle is one of the most influential factors determining the moduli of nanocomposites, provided the other conditions such as dispersion state are similar Compared with?.

Table no 2. Intensities of D and G bands for CNT A and CNT B before and after UV/ozone treatment

CNT Type	Exposure time	Position of D Band	Position of G Band	I_D/I_G
	Min	Cm ⁻¹	Cm ⁻¹	
CNT A	0	1330	1581	0.87
	30	1340	1581	1.06
	60	1330	1575	1.11
	120	1331	1579	1.13
CNT B	0	1342	1573	0.8
	30	1342	1573	0.86
	60	1342	1572	0.86
	120	1341	1571	0.87

Fig5: (a) Flexural strength and (b) flexural modulus of nanocomposites as a function of CNT content of two different sources. Data for CNT B after [8].

3.4 Electrical Conductivity of Nanocomposites

The electrical conductivity is plotted as function of CNT content (Fig 6) along with the corresponding data for CNT B. The electrical conductivity of nanocomposites with CNT A remained almost constant and there was no clear percolation observed within the range of CNT content studied (i.e. between 0 and 0.7wt%). It appears that the improved CNT dispersion was not beneficial for electrical conductivity of these nanocomposites. The poor inherent electrical conductivity of CNT A was mainly responsible for non-conducting behaviour of nanocomposites with CNT B, which was because of the large amorphous carbon layers on the surface of these carbon nanotubes. The presence of large amorphous carbon layers on CNTs did not support the formation of π electron networks required for electrical conduction. The silane treated CNTs (CNT B) also exhibited poor electrical conductivity because wrapping of epoxy chains over the entire wall of CNTs prevented charge transfer between the adjacent CNTs.

Fig 6: Electrical conductivities of nanocomposites as a function of CNT content of two different sources. Data for CNT B after [8].

3.5 Glass transition temperature of Nanocomposite

The glass transition temperatures, T_g , determined from the $\tan \delta$ curves of materials from the DMA analysis are shown in Fig. 7. It was found that both the T_g generally increased with increasing CNT content. The silane-treated CNT B nanocomposites, however, exhibited much higher values than the CNT A nanocomposites. The heavily functionalised CNTs by the silane coupling agent resulted in strong covalent bonds with the epoxy matrix, giving rise to a higher degree of constraints to polymer molecular movements especially at high temperatures compared with CNT A.

Fig.7 Glass transition temperature of nanocomposites as a function of CNT content of two different sources. Data for CNT B after [8].

3.6. Impact Toughness of nanocomposites

The average impact fracture toughness of nanocomposites for neat epoxy and CNT s/epoxy nanocomposites are shown in Fig. 8. There was a remarkable twofold enhancement of toughness, from 2.9 to 5.8 KJ/m², for 0.3 wt% CNT A nanocomposites. Further increase in the CNT content of the nanocomposites did not result in much improvement. To identify the toughening mechanisms responsible for the improvement due to CNTs, the fracture surfaces were examined and SEM images are presented in Fig 9. Major differences in the morphologies of the neat epoxy and CNT nanocomposites could be identified. The neat epoxy (Fig. 9a) exhibited a smooth fracture surface with small-sized, repetitive patterns representing typical brittle failure of epoxy while a much rougher morphology with a large, radically extended crack pattern could be seen on the fracture surface of the 0.3wt% CNT nanocomposites [3]. Judging from the similar impact fracture toughness of the nanocomposites, the fracture morphologies of the composites with 0.5wt% and 0.7wt% CNTs were also similar to 0.3% CNT nanocomposites. Surface roughness of the neat epoxy and nanocomposites were measured using an optical profiler and the results are given in Table 3. The values of R_a , representing the mean height calculated over the entire measured area, increased from 0.12 μ m for neat epoxy to 2.9 μ m for 0.3 wt % nanocomposites. With further increase in CNT content, there was a marginal increase in

both R_a and R_t , confirming the saturation of impact fracture toughness at about 0.3wt% CNT.

Fig. 8. Impact toughness of nanocomposites

Fig 9 Fracture surface morphologies of (a) neat epoxy and nanocomposites containing (b) 0.3wt% CNT and (c) 0.7wt% CNT

Table 3: Surface roughness of neat epoxy and CNT A nanocomposites

Materials	Roughness, R_a (μm)	Max. Height, R_t (μm)
Neat epoxy	0.12	1.68
0.3wt%CNT/epoxy	2.9	23.9
0.5wt%CNT/epoxy	3.3	24.0
0.7wt%CNT/epoxy	3.4 μm	24.05 μm

4. CONCLUSION

Multi-walled carbon nanotubes with a dual wall structure were characterized and used as a nano-reinforcement in epoxy to fabricate nanocomposites. The effects of the turbostatic structure of CNT on the mechanical, thermal and electrical properties of epoxy composites with different CNT contents were studied and compared with those made from thin-walled CNTs. The major findings from this study are highlighted as follows:

1. XPS and Raman analyses after UV/O treatment indicated that the CNT with turbostatic structure could be easily functionalized. UV/Ozone exposure of 30 min was sufficient to impart necessary surface functionalities.
2. The above finding confirmed improved interfacial interactions with polymer resins due to covalent bonding between the CNTs and epoxy resin.
3. Epoxy-based nanocomposites containing CNTs exhibited better flexural strength and fracture resistance than those made from thin-walled CNTs.
4. The electrical conductivity of nanocomposites containing CNTs with dual wall structure was lower than that of thin-walled CNTs because of the presence of large non-conducting amorphous carbon layers on the dual wall surface.

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